

Bias and Entropy

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Entropy is often associated with maximum disorder, but we try to consider it in terms of minimum bias or equal frequency in the sense that a higher frequency for an event compared to others leads to bias and less entropy. We first consider this using Shannon's entropy = $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ with no constraints and then investigate the origin of this expression.

We next consider the idea of a gas of N particles and energy E . In order to remove bias, one might argue that all $f(e_i)$, where e_i is single particle energy should be the same for all e_i , but this leads to problems due to the constraint of E , i.e. $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$. Thus, $f(e_i)$'s are not constant. If two body elastic collisions occur, however, one may apply the notion to the product of probabilities $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ and try to remove bias from the collisions. Shannon's entropy considerations above dictate that $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ should be a constant if $e_1+e_2=E$ constant. This result, however, is equivalent to a maximization of entropy for arrangements if one enforces independence of $f(e_i)$.

One may show specifically that this result equals the maximization of arrangement $sN! / \text{Product over } i (Nf(e_i))!$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$.

Entropy and Bias

Consider n possible outcomes with the same weight, i.e. the same frequency, $P(i) = 1/n$. This seems to represent a lack of bias.

Next consider changing the frequencies of the outcomes to the n vector $\{j\}$ such that $\sum_j j = n$. If one considers Shannon's entropy: $S = -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ then:

No bias $S = \ln(n)$ ((1a)) while $-\sum_i j/n \ln(j/n) = \ln(n) - \sum_{j \geq 1} j/n \ln j$ where $j \geq 1$ ((1b))

((1b)) < ((1a)). ((2))

This means equal weights or frequencies (i.e. less bias) lead to maximum Shannon's entropy and explains why a 6 sided die represents more Shannon's entropy than a coin with 2 outcomes.

Shannon's entropy expression follows from considering a large N number of independent outcomes. If N is very large, the number of times an outcome i with $P(i)$ occurs is $NP(i)$. Thus, the probability for a run of N outcomes is:

Probability = $\text{Product over } i P(i)^{NP(i)}$ ((3a))

$\ln(\text{Probability}) = \sum_i NP(i) \ln(P(i))$ ((3b))

Thus, entropy is related to the product probability of a run of outcomes. If there is no bias in the probabilities, one maximizes Shannon's entropy as shown above. In the above, one lets $N \rightarrow$ infinite.

Even though Shannon's entropy was obtained for a product scenario above, one may obtain the form in a manner which does not involve a product of probabilities. Consider N particles subject to an additive constraint such that each particle has a property a_i such that $\sum a_i = \text{Constant}$. If one distributes the constant to the N particles in a certain way, i.e. vector $\{a_i\}$, one may create the unique arrangements:

$$\text{Number of unique arrangements} = N! / \text{Product } n(a_i)! \quad ((4))$$

This again is related to the idea of frequency or weight because $n(a_i)$ is the number of particles which receive the same amount a_i . From the above considerations one would like to have all particles obtain the same a_i so there is no bias, but there is also the constraint $\sum a_i = \text{Constant}$ where $N f(a_i) = n(a_i)$.

If $N \rightarrow$ infinite, $n(a_i)$ is large and one may use Stirling's approximation i.e. $\ln\{n(a_i)!\} = n(a_i) \ln(n(a_i))$. ((5)).

((5)), however, is Shannon's entropy and we showed above that it is maximized for probabilities if one minimizes bias among the weights. In this case, one may try to maximize the \ln of the number of arrangements subject to the constraint as well. This leads to:

Maximize: $-\sum n(a_i) \ln(n(a_i)) + 1/T \sum a_i n(a_i) \rightarrow n(a_i) = C \exp(-a_i/T)$ where $1/T$ is a Lagrange multiplier. ((6))

Thus, the constraint affects the result.

The Case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

The example ((6)) is the result for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas for $a_i = e_i$, single particle energy. We, however, consider the problem in a different way. We argued that Shannon's entropy maximization suggests the removal of bias. This seems to suggest that:

$$f(e_i) = \text{constant} \quad ((7))$$

The problem with ((7)) is the constraint $\sum e_i f(e_i) = E$. One cannot have $f(e_i) = \text{constant}$. How does one use the idea of a lack of bias or equal weights?

We argue that it occurs through the notion of physical elastic two-body collisions. For a given $E = e_i + e_j$, one has:

$$P(i,j) = P(e_i)P(e_j) \quad ((8))$$

If one applies the notion of Shannon's entropy to $P(i,j)$ for a given E_1 , the constraint is already incorporated in $e_i + e_j = E_1$. Maximum Shannon's entropy means no bias or different frequencies, so all $P(i,j)$'s for a given E_1 must be equal. Thus: $P(e_i)P(e_j) = \text{constant}$. Taking \ln yields:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) + \ln(P(e_j)) = \ln(\text{constant}) \quad ((9)) \text{ which may be compared with } e_i + e_j = E_1.$$

A solution is: $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. We consider this in more detail.

$P(e_i)$ may be part of various $E(i)$ situations i.e. $P(e_i)P(e_j) = E_1$, $P(e_i)P(e_k) = E_2$ etc, so the result should be independent for i and j , but as it stands, ((9)) is not. If one multiplies $e_i + e_j = E_1$ by a constant, b , and subtracts this from ((9)),:

$$\{ \ln(P(e_i)) - be_i \} + \{ \ln(P(e_j)) - b \} = \ln(\text{constant}) - bE_1 \quad ((10))$$

To have independence one needs $\{ \ln(P(e_i)) - be_i \} = 0$. This is of the form of a maximization result for a single particle as shown above. This means that:

$$\ln(\text{constant}) - bE_1 = 0 \text{ or } \text{constant} = \exp(E_1 b) \text{ One may set } b = -1/T \text{ because } b \text{ is a constant.} \quad ((11))$$

There is consistency. Thus, the idea of independence of particles combined with a lack of bias (no unequal frequencies from Shannon's entropy) for product probabilities is equivalent to maximization of Shannon's entropy for a single particle probability subject to a constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$, not product probabilities. Maximizing Shannon's entropy for product probabilities appears to be equivalent to maximizing if for a single particle as shown in ((10)), ((11)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may introduce the idea of removing bias or unequal weights or frequencies. This requires a measure which demonstrates that increasing weights/frequencies decreases the measure's value. Shannon's entropy seems to represent this function as we demonstrate because a set of equal probabilities $1/n$ always has a greater entropy than the set $\{j/n\}$ where $j \geq 1$ and $\sum_j j = n$. We demonstrate various ways of obtaining the Shannon's entropy form.

For the case of N gas particles with a total energy E , we argue that one cannot set $f(e_i) = \text{constant}$ due to the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$. We thus ask: How does the notion of no bias or equal weights come into play? We suggest it must enter through a consideration which does not use the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i) = E$. One may consider two body collisions such that $e_i + e_j = E_1$. In such a case, one picks a set of e_i, e_j pairs such that $e_i + e_j = E_1$. There should be no bias for those pairs according to Shannon's entropy considerations, so $f(e_i)f(e_j) = \text{joint probability}$ should be a constant value based on E_1 to maximize entropy. We suggest that imposing independence on $f(e_i)$ and $f(e_j)$ implies that one have the form: $\ln(f(e_i)) - be_i = 0$ where b is a constant. Thus, the equal weight idea applied to a product probability (which is consistent

with Shannon's entropy with no outside constraint) collapses to a maximization of Shannon's entropy with the constraint $\sum_i e_i f(e_i)$.

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